

HIGH JUMP DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS SCHOOL STUDENTS IN VOLLEYBALL TRAINING

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Abstract: *This article discusses the problems of developing the qualities of jumping and jump endurance of volleyball players of children and youth sports schools.*

Key words: *Children and adolescents, jumping, physical qualities, volleyball, exercise.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы развития прыжковых качеств и прыжковой выносливости у волейболистов детско-юношеских спортивных школ.*

Ключевые слова: *Дети и подростки, прыжки, физические качества, волейбол, физические упражнения.*

Anotatsiya: *Ушбу мақолада болалар ва ўсмирлар спорт мактаблари волейболчиларининг сакровчанлик ва сакраш чидамкорлиги сифатларини ривожлантириши муаммолари ҳақида фикрлар билдирилган.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Болалар ва ўсмирлар, сакраш, жисмоний сифатлар, волейболчилар, жисмоний машқлар.*

At present, the country is undergoing significant reforms in the training of young talented athletes, creating all the conditions for regular participation in sports and holding local and national competitions on the basis of current official rules.

It is known that the main strategic problem in this area is to create a scientific and methodological basis for the training of young, competitive athletes. However, this process is very complex, comprehensive and multifaceted in its organizational and technological aspects, and requires the organization of a phased and consistent approach.

In sports practice, including in the initial stage of training athletes, it is seen that the methodology of developing physical qualities, which is the basis of sportsmanship, is often based on the preference for the use of general or specific physical exercises. However, pushing for such exercises can lead to certain negative consequences. This

is because the standardized application of these exercises in a certain volume, intensity and duration does not always allow to take into account the level of physical and functional condition of children. Consequently, such a method of developing physical qualities can lead to stress, rapid fatigue, and even symptoms of illness in the learner. In the prevention of such complications and the development of physical qualities, the predominance of non-standard games, exercises was observed.

But, which exercise has more of such an advantage?

The scientific novelty of the research is:

- A specific set of non-standard exercises was selected and tested;
- The effectiveness of the selected exercises was determined;
- The advantage of selected non-standard exercises over general and special physical exercises in the formation of speed-strength (jumping) qualities was identified.

The initial training phase consists of determining the effectiveness of the formation of speed-strength (jumping) qualities of 10-11-year-old volleyball players using non-standard game exercises.

This goal was achieved on the basis of the following tasks:

1. To study the level of use of movement games in the training of young athletes;
2. To determine the effectiveness of selected non-standard exercises in the development of agility-strength (jumping, fast running) qualities of young athletes;
3. Based on the results of the study, we set ourselves the goal of developing methodological recommendations and their application in the practice of athletes.

Targeted physical training in the training of qualified volleyball players in children's and youth sports schools is one of the most important factors in the formation of technical and tactical skills and high results during the competition. However, in sports practice, it is often the case that planned exercise does not give the expected result in the development of appropriate movement qualities. One of the main reasons for this is the lack of objective assessment of the volume and intensity of exercise used in training and the degree of impact of these indicators on the body of the trainee. taking into account the possibility of planning this load in accordance with the purpose.

In the training of qualified volleyball players in sports schools for children and adolescents, special attention is paid to two interrelated aspects of the movement function:

- Training and improvement of technical and tactical skills of the athlete;
- training of physical qualities of the athlete according to features of the chosen sport.

According to VN Platonov, the concept of general physical training refers to the level of comprehensive (harmonious) development of the qualities of movement of the athlete. Such an approach to the issue is expedient from the point of view of shaping the health of ordinary people (including athletes). Of course, this is also necessary in big sports.

However, such practice and training methods based on it are likely to reduce the effectiveness of training qualified athletes and achieving high results. Because each sport has its own unique and unique characteristics, the quality of endurance plays a leading role in one sport, while the quality of endurance plays a leading role in a second sport, or the quality of flexibility in a third sport. However, this does not mean that certain physical qualities are essential in one sport and not important in another. On the contrary, each quality will have a more or less significant share in a particular sporting situation.

In the training of qualified volleyball players, especially the qualities of speed and strength (jumping, jogging) play an important role, and in the process of training these qualities play an important role in the formation of movement games.

Demonstrating effective play and achieving high results in modern volleyball can only be achieved at the expense of well-developed physical qualities. In this regard, the quality of endurance, including game endurance and jump endurance, is particularly important. According to V.A. Titar, the most important physical quality for volleyball players is jump endurance. However, no matter what special endurance (jumping, playing, speed endurance) it can be formed only on the basis of general endurance. It is therefore advisable to analyze the scientific data on the problems of developing endurance in general along with the quality of agility. It should be noted that the effectiveness of the formation of sports training depends directly on the development of all physical qualities that are interconnected. Another important condition in this regard is that the level of development of physical qualities should be assessed using appropriate test exercises.

Innovative aimed at improving the quality of jumping

M.I. Popichev, who proposed the method, tried this method on young volleyball players. He divided these volleyball players into 4 groups according to the length of their body joints:

- 1) children with short legs and long hips and body;
- 2) children with long hips and short legs;
- 3) long-legged and short-legged and children;
- 4) children with short hips and long stature and legs.

It was with these morphological features in mind that the children in each group underwent a specific majority of jumping exercises, and after a certain period of time, the effectiveness of these exercises was examined.

M.Boyirbekov, who for many years has been observing the growth of jumping endurance of qualified volleyball players, managed to draw a number of conclusions of scientific and practical significance. In particular, he said, high-skilled volleyball players jumped 306 to 600 times during a game to strike and block. The maximum number of jumps to perform these skills is 4 parties (142 times). Jumping to put an obstacle (122) is more than jumping to hit, as long as it is repeated (113 times). Observations show that the number of jumps performed during a single training session is less than the number of jumps per competition.

Therefore, the training of highly qualified volleyball players and the promotion of sports skills to a high level is directly related to the effectiveness of the initial training process.

In recent years, a radical change in the rules of volleyball competitions has given a completely new look to the performance of game activities and game skills. Nowadays, almost all game skills are performed in most situations "in the air", ie jumping (kicking, blocking, entering the ball, passing, receiving the ball, falling). The occurrence of this condition not only enhances the focus on the qualities of jumping and jump endurance in volleyball practice,

rather, it requires the creation of new scientific technologies aimed at the rapid development of these qualities.

In conclusion, we can say that in the process of many years of sports training, the effectiveness of training qualified volleyball players in children's and youth sports schools is to create new ways to perfectly develop the qualities of jumping and endurance.

The scope of scientific research and scientific literature covering the problems of developing volleyball jumping and jump endurance is very wide.

The rapid updating of indicators in modern world sports requires the search for new, more effective means, methods and forms of training young athletes.

The training of highly qualified volleyball players depends primarily on the pace of development of physical qualities. That is, the more these qualities are formed, the more effective the level of development of technical and tactical skills of participants, regardless of age.

In this regard, it was once again recognized that the qualities of jumping and special agility are inextricably linked with the indicators of technical and tactical training, and that these qualities play an important role in the progressive development of sportsmanship.

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